

WEB3 FOR UKRAINE: UPGRADING PUBLIC SERVICES

Ministry
of Digital Transformation
of Ukraine

SUMMARY

In the past few years, a significant number of web3 pilots were launched in the Ukrainian public sector with varying degrees of success. This study provides a retrospective analysis of those projects and offers insights and recommendations for the success of future digital initiatives.

The web3 projects identified in this study span multiple sectors, including finance, supply chain, transportation, auctions, and land and property registration. Their common goals were to create verifiable credentials, reduce fraud, and protect critical information networks from cyber threats. However, only two of the seven projects studied progressed beyond the pilot stage, and most encountered scaling hurdles.

Our insights for future projects relate to project management efficiency, technology solutions costs, awareness among decision-makers, as well as security and clarity within the regulatory environment for project participants. The recommendations emphasize the need for technological standardization, education, advocacy, planning for scale, and impact measurement. Further explorations might be needed to uncover the systemic challenges posed by web3, including human rights protection, international law compliance, new attack vectors, etc.

The target audience for this research includes public officials, businesses, and donors involved in web3 integration projects in government services. It is also intended to inform future strategies for the Innovation Sandbox developed by the Ministry of Digital Transformation.

Keywords: digital economy, web3, blockchain, distributed ledger technology, public services, government projects, public administration, public-private partnership.

INTRODUCTION

Relevance

Web3 technologies have become an innovative tool for advancing government priorities and public sector applications. When applied strategically, blockchain infrastructure can enhance digital trust and information security, it can accelerate a government's goals related to citizen trust in digital transformation. Blockchain can facilitate connections between private organizations and public agencies, improving efficiency and transparency in government administration.

The increasing regulatory clarity over web3, through acknowledgment by governments and regulators globally, has created essential frameworks. These clearer guidelines establish a more favorable environment, promoting responsible growth for blockchain-based startups and enterprises, as well as wider adoption, driven by the growing interest of individuals and businesses in decentralized solutions¹.

Governments, both within the European Union² and globally³, have already developed comprehensive nation-scale frameworks for integrating web3 and blockchain into public administration. While these strategy documents vary in length and content, they share common points. Most roadmaps emphasize areas such as

- regulation and standards regarding identity, privacy, and security;
- international investment and collaboration for exploring sectoral opportunities;
- innovation encouragement, especially in the financial sector, while ensuring stability;
- advancing projects with proven solutions and utilizing regulatory sandboxes.

In the Ukrainian context, we have several national development strategies, including the main one for the economy⁴ and concept document on artificial intelligence⁵, as well as several legal initiatives to regulate the circulation of virtual assets⁶. Although the latter aims to create a favorable environment for the growth of the web3 industry, increase budget revenues, and improve Ukraine's investment appeal by aligning with European standards for crypto asset regulation (MiCA) and adapting FATF recommendations for financial monitoring, there is currently no comprehensive overview of the web3 sector's development.

It is important to mention that despite the enduring war with Russia⁷, Ukraine has become a significant player in the web3 landscape, ranking among the top ten globally in terms of adoption indexes for crypto⁸ and decentralized finance⁹. Ukraine remains

¹ [Global Protocol Report 2024](#)

² [European Commission, Germany, Netherlands, Switzerland](#)

³ [Australia, UK, US, Canada, India](#)

⁴ [Національна економічна стратегія на період до 2030 року](#)

⁵ [Концепція розвитку штучного інтелекту в Україні](#)

⁶ [Про віртуальні активи \(Закон України, що не набрав чинності\)](#)

⁷ [Global Conflict Tracker: War in Ukraine](#)

⁸ [The 2023 Global Crypto Adoption Index](#)

⁹ [DeFi Adoption Index](#)

committed to web3 innovation. In the summer of 2022, Ukraine was accepted as an observer in the European Blockchain Partnership¹⁰. This partnership aims to implement blockchain technology in governmental registries and services through collaborative efforts. Under the European Blockchain Partnership, Ukraine is the 30th country to leverage blockchain for cross-border public services and the second outside the European Union, following Norway. In addition, the Ministry of Digital Transformation aims to provide government services online, a crucial aspect of Ukraine's war strategy¹¹ and a prerequisite for the widespread governmental adoption of blockchain-enabled applications.

Recent reports including Foresight¹² and Talk to Founders¹³ have identified the need to advance the usage of web3 technology within a Sandbox environment. Enabling a sandbox environment aims to encourage public-private cooperation and support innovative business models and infrastructure associated with web3 technologies. This approach recognizes innovative organizational structures enabled by blockchain and decentralized governance and addresses the need to provide economic stability and potentially attract investment within the ecosystem. During the preliminary research stage, it was discovered that the creation of an effective sandbox requires significant effort and collaboration between the public and private sectors. The sandbox should be a flexible environment, free of legal and technical barriers, with the ability for smooth expansion. It should also integrate seamlessly with ongoing state digital initiatives such as Diia-City or E-residency. Overall, the objective is to assist startups by providing them with state-backed opportunities to test their business concepts.

Objectives of the Study

This research aims to broaden the understanding of the current applications of web3 in government initiatives in Ukraine. The report's primary objective is to provide decision-makers with information for the strategic integration of blockchain technologies in the government services sector. The report aims to enhance understanding of how public-private partnerships in web3 contribute to the efficient functioning of public administration. The report may be useful to individuals in related fields or those interested in the adoption of blockchain technologies at the government level.

To achieve this goal, the following main research objectives were set:

- to provide a contextual understanding of foreign experiences through a review of global literature on the adoption of web3 in government;
- to analyze various web3 government pilot projects in Ukraine, highlighting their background, progress, notable successes, and shortcomings;

¹⁰ [Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine. News from June 17, 2022](#)

¹¹ [Analyzing the Role of Blockchain Technology in Strengthening Democracies](#)

¹² [Foresight: Virtual Assets 2030 Report](#)

¹³ [WEB3! Web3 for Ukraine - Talk to Founders](#)

- to propose recommendations contributing to the overall understanding of the analyzed projects for the success of future pilot projects.

Considering ongoing initiatives in the public sector and global technological advancements, it is relevant to discuss web3 technologies¹⁴ with the understanding that blockchain technology and solutions and services built upon it constitute a foundational pillar of web3.

Research Methodology

The research uses a structured approach that included desk research and interviews with project representatives, primarily high-level managers, and technical specialists. Desk research questions used to select representative projects included:

- Project object and scope. The first criterion in the project selection process was the implementation of projects designed to test blockchain technology and enhance existing public services.
- Project stage. Projects in the proof of concept or prototype stage were excluded from the study, while those entering the pilot stage were retained based on the second selection characteristic.

Therefore, seven cases were specifically selected to represent different areas of blockchain implementation, including land and property registration, auctions, supply chains, transportation, and payments.

Interviews with project representatives focused on analyzing specific challenges encountered during project implementation, exploring key factors that contributed to success or failure, and identifying obstacles in the process.

¹⁴ [WEB3I Web3 for Ukraine - Talk to Founders](#)

INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE OVERVIEW

This chapter of the study examines global literature on the use of blockchain in public services, providing generalizations that may apply to the analysis of specific projects in Ukraine. The selection criteria included insights and summaries from various papers and reports that depict global implementations, including research methodologies, approaches, and innovative ideas related to the implementation of blockchain technologies in public services.

The literature on web3 in the public sector explores the transformative potential of blockchain technology across various governmental domains, including digital currencies, electronic voting systems, notarization services, asset and collateral registries, land registries, verification of document authenticity (diplomas), storage of personal records: birth, marriage, death, and others¹⁵. All of these have a few common goals, which are aimed at achieving easily verifiable information, thus ensuring the reduction of fraud (in verification, budget payments, tax collecting, etc.), as well as the protection of key information networks from cyberattacks.

Currently, there is no widely available index of blockchain deployments in government at various levels. In the literature on blockchain adoption, many studies rely on the theoretical technological, organizational, and environmental (TOE) framework originally proposed by Louis G. Tornatzky and Mitchell Fleischer in 1990. It is a widely used approach for studying technology adoption in the information systems field as a whole, examining the challenges between technological advances, organizational dynamics, and environmental influences¹⁶. The challenges in the aforementioned areas related to blockchain technology in public services can be presented in the following table¹⁷:

Technological challenges	Organizational challenges	Environmental challenges
Design issues Scalability Process change cost Low throughput rate Security	Resistance to change Capacity-building Technical skills	Enabling legislative support Lack of awareness Legal issues Collaboration among government agencies

The current landscape of blockchain adoption in the public sector is characterized by the following:

- consists of isolated initiatives, unique to the particular circumstances of the country, municipality, etc;

¹⁵ [Blockchain for Governments: The Case of the Dubai Government](#)

¹⁶ [The technology–organization–environment framework](#)

¹⁷ [A Hierarchical Framework of Challenges for Blockchain Adoption in Public Services. Implications for decision-makers](#)

- active experimentation, a crucial stage in the adoption process, is often in decline;¹⁸
- discrepancy between stated goals and achieved results, coupled with inconsistencies in the chosen technology stack, architecture, and use of blockchain to achieve stated goals.

The public sector has a unique role as a trusted party, and blockchain's potential to support or challenge this role may very well have an impact on adoption. From this perspective, overcoming resistance emerges as a critical factor in blockchain adoption, requiring a focus on demonstrating value and addressing concerns. Future adopters are advised to rely on project outcomes, technological advancements, and appropriate partnerships, emphasizing the need for ongoing engagement with legal experts to navigate regulatory complexities¹⁹. This last point seems particularly important, as studies consistently confirm that the influence of the regulatory environment was cited by numerous projects as significant and lacking clarity. The examples set by countries such as Estonia²⁰ and the United Arab Emirates (UAE)²¹ in deploying blockchain applications in government show that the creation of a legal framework that recognizes electronic transactions, digital identities, digital contracts, and the automated execution of contracts is key to the adoption of web3 in public services.

The basic idea of successful implementation of blockchain technologies in public services is still subject to the main general idea: as future outcomes become apparent, there will be a subsequent increase in support. Therefore, when examining the adoption of blockchain for governance, case studies provide a particularly appropriate method to explore this emerging phenomenon in its authentic context.

¹⁸ [New Kid On The Block! Understanding Blockchain Adoption in the Public Sector](#)

¹⁹ [There can be found a good example: Public service operational efficiency and blockchain – A case study of Companies House, UK](#)

²⁰ [Blockchain-based application at a governmental level: disruption or illusion? The case of Estonia](#)

²¹ [Blockchain for Governments: The Case of the Dubai Government](#)

UKRAINIAN PILOTS OVERVIEW

This chapter of the study provides a brief introduction to the projects selected for detailed review in the following sections. Additionally, it offers a concise summary of other public-private initiatives aimed at implementing web3 technology solutions in government services, particularly in the context of the ongoing war conflict in Ukraine.

During the initial stage of implementing blockchain in public services in Ukraine, pilot projects were conducted in areas such as real estate property rights registration, auctions for the sale of seized property, and product supply chain management. The pilot projects initiated by the Government of Ukraine in 2017 under Government Directive No. 353-r, which introduced blockchain technology into the System of Electronic Trading in Arrested Property (SETAM), the State Register of Property Rights to Real Estate, and the State Service of Ukraine for Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre, should be considered as the early adopters. Simultaneously, research and preparations were made for the future e-Hryvnia project that will be tested for the first time in 2018. Alongside these initiatives, the next pilot cases to be considered are product supply chain traceability with Tradelens in 2020-2021 and Forest Stewardship Council in 2022. The respective sections of the research describe these specific projects.

In addition to the areas where web3 is commonly used in public services, there are some special cases involving blockchain technology that have not been selected for research but are still worth mentioning. For example, the use of blockchain technology for online donations has resulted in significant funding for Ukrainian fundraising initiatives around the world: specifically, humanitarian causes received \$73 million, while campaigns with a military focus accumulated \$114 million in cryptocurrency donations²². It is important to note that cryptocurrencies were also used as payment in some procurement cases, such as the acquisition of drones from European suppliers by local volunteer groups.

The United Nations Refugee Agency received the Best Impact Project Award at Paris Blockchain Week 2023 for a pilot project in Ukraine that utilized blockchain technology to provide financial assistance to displaced individuals. The assistance was convertible to cash and could be used for rent, food, utilities, and medical expenses²³.

Also, Web3 technology has proven to be valuable to Ukraine beyond just finance. Starling Lab's 'Dokaz' project²⁴ has created a framework for documenting war crimes and genocide using open-source tools and best practices from web3 technologies. The issue at hand is the reliability and admissibility of digital evidence in legal proceedings, specifically about war crimes committed during the Russian invasion of Ukraine. The project offers a practical solution for securely capturing, storing, and

²² [Report on Crypto Donations Raised in Support of Ukraine](#)

²³ [United Nations Ukraine](#)

²⁴ [Trustless Evidence: Web3 is helping document war crimes in Ukraine](#)

verifying digital content to address the technical and ethical challenges of establishing trust in digital records originating from Ukraine²⁵.

Below is given a more detailed analysis of the pilot projects, using the methodology described above. The in-depth examination aims to provide a broad understanding of the project's implementation, successes, and challenges within the context of our study.

SETAM & OpenMarket Auctions

Date live: 2017-2020

Stakeholders: Ministry of Justice, State Enterprise "SETAM", East Europe Foundation, Bitfury Group

Problem: Restricting retroactive changes to completed auctions is crucial for preventing potential data manipulation and ensuring transparent access to bid information for all participants.

Solution: In response to this challenge, Ukraine's Government initiated the implementation of blockchain technology into the System of Electronic Trading in Arrested Property managed by the [State Enterprise "SETAM"](#) of the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine. The SETAM rebranded then into OpenMarket, conducting auctions from September 7, 2017, to 2020, leveraging distributed ledger technology through the [Exonum blockchain framework](#). All auctions were hashed and saved in the Bitcoin blockchain. The mechanism of this technology was the following: the information that comes to the system is stored on several private nodes and a public server. Thus, everyone can observe the trading process in real-time without the risk of data loss. Information was checked on each step of the trading by copying the transaction hash code and inserting it in the appropriate field at www.blockchain.gov.ua, then the system issues a complete list of rates: volume, size, date of a bid that was made. Supported by the [East Europe Foundation](#) (Ukraine) and in collaboration with [BitFury Group](#), the project demonstrated the viability of blockchain technology in state-level initiatives without requiring additional legislative conditions.

Results: According to the OpenMarket report from April 2020, OpenMarket successfully conducted 26,403 auctions from 2017 to 2020, generating more than UAH 7 billion through the use of blockchain technology²⁶. The average value of each lot increased from 12% to 18%. The most expensive lot sold was the abandoned Arsenal plant building, which was auctioned for UAH 563 million. This use of blockchain provided benefits such as increased security, resistance to cyber attacks, prevention of node failures, real-time process monitoring, protection against historical data tampering, and increased trust from auction participants.

²⁵ [Project Dokaz](#)

²⁶ [SETAM продав майна за допомогою blockchain на 6 млрд грн.](#)

However, the announced results have attracted some criticism because the Exonum blockchain nodes were not sufficiently decentralized and remained only under OpenMarket's control²⁷. It is important to mention that this project is unusual among early adopters in that its economic impact was evaluated. However, the evaluation is difficult to confirm due to the lack of disclosed research methodologies.

The State Land Cadastre

Date live: 2017-2018

Stakeholders: State Land Cadastre, State E-Governance Agency of Ukraine, Bitfury Group, Transparency International Ukraine

Problem: The Ukrainian property registry system is comprised of two electronic registries: the State Land Cadastre and the State Registry of Property Rights on Immovable Property. Historically, schemes involving the seizure of land by raiders took advantage of weaknesses in the State Land Cadastre in Ukraine. As of October 2017, the State Land Cadastre had registered 18.8 million land plots, containing information about their legal owners.²⁸ The lack of synchronization between the State Registry of Property Rights on Immovable Property and the State Land Cadastre can lead to legal consequences and potential fraud. In addition, there's a constant need to elevate the overall value of agricultural land per hectare, which corresponds to the prosperity of landowners in Ukraine.

Solution: An attempt to solve this problem dates back to the summer of 2017 when the State E-Governance Agency of Ukraine and world-leading blockchain infrastructure provider [BitFury](#) signed a memorandum of cooperation to transfer the State Land Cadastre to blockchain²⁹. In the late fall of 2017, according to loud media headlines, "the land cadastre in Ukraine has been transferred to blockchain technology,"³⁰ although this statement did not correspond to reality, as only a demo version of the prototype was launched.

The technical implementation of the project was supported by BitFury, and the international anti-corruption organization [Transparency International Ukraine](#), which provided expert assistance in the implementation of the technology. This organization also became an external node auditor of the correctness of the system. The system³¹ for storing, generating, and verifying land registry extracts was based on the [Exonum](#) blockchain framework, built on open-source code and under the Apache license. In

²⁷ [Government by Code? Blockchain Applications to Public Sector Governance](#)

²⁸ [Blockchain seen as boost to transparency, owners](#)

²⁹ [BitFury to Help in Moving Ukraine's Land Registry to Blockchain](#)

³⁰ [Державний земельний кадастр перейшов на технологію Blockchain](#)

³¹ Upon receipt of a cadastral extract, all relevant data related to a particular land plot - cadastral number, location, purpose, area, ownership, owners, and tenants - were recorded in the blockchain database, and each cadastral extract was accompanied by a separate sheet. In addition, a blockchain hash - a unique identifier in the blockchain database - and a QR code were attached to each cadastral extract. This allowed anyone to verify the accuracy of the information on the extract by entering the hash on the dedicated website or downloading an electronic version of the extract.

this way, the State Land Cadastre became the second public sector project in Ukraine to use blockchain technology³².

Results: In the State Land Cadastre blockchain technology has provided the ability to identify the authenticity of a given document and easily verify the information in the registry through the hash-check thus ensuring some form of public online control over the authenticity of land registry extracts. However, key processes for registering land rights, such as the electronic database and transaction history, were not migrated to the blockchain or other distributed ledger technology.

At the time of this project, Exonum's blockchain framework functionality did not allow land transaction information to be stored on the blockchain other than data hashing and hash control. In addition, there was resistance to the project within the State Land Cadastre system because it exposed certain corrupt practices in the context of land transactions, including state-owned land in Ukraine. Technical problems and resistance within the system were the reasons why this pilot project was stopped at the first stage of implementation.

Vehicle IDs registry

Pilot Dates: 2017 (initiated) – Present (yet to be launched)

Stakeholders: Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine, Vareger, Andromeda, TAPAS, East Europe Foundation

Problem: In the pursuit of enhancing the certification and authorization of imported vehicles, a project was initiated to improve the management of registries containing type certificates and conformity certificates for wheeled vehicles, their components, and equipment.

Solution: The proposed solution involved the implementation of an experimental project scheduled to run until March 31, 2021, leveraging the Hyperledger framework and integration with id.gov.ua.

Results: Despite the initial intentions, the project faced challenges before the launch and hasn't yet yielded the expected results. Currently, there is a need for an update with the integration APIs and the protocol that has been developed since.

TradeLens Container Logistics

Date live: 2017-2023

Stakeholders: State Customs Service, A.P. Moller-Maersk, IBM, GIZ

³² [Державний земельний кадастр перейшов на технологію Blockchain](#)

Problem: In the container logistics industry, stakeholders such as operators, port authorities, shippers, and forwarders face several challenges. The reliance on traditional paper-based logistics documents introduces errors and delays in port processes. The manual handling of documents leads to inaccuracies, double-checks, and corrections, increasing the risk of disruptions at the port of destination. In the absence of streamlined information sharing, the ecosystem faces inefficiencies and a lack of transparency. In addition, the opaque nature of customs processes and the potential for delays contribute to a lack of trust among supply chain participants.

Solution: TradeLens, a joint initiative by A.P. Moller-Maersk, an integrated logistics company, and IBM launched the blockchain-based platform in 2016. This platform was used by more than 150 participants to organize container logistics and cargo tracking. The TradeLens ecosystem included more than 100 seaports and port operators, 20+ sea carriers and intermodal operators (carriers that transport goods by several modes of transport), 10+ countries' customs offices (including Ukraine³³), and one of the leading international banking groups. TradeLens addressed the problems mentioned earlier by providing real-time tracking capabilities and transparent information sharing.

In Ukraine TradeLens began testing back in 2020, as at that time shipping lines integrated into Tradelens occupied more than 50% of the Ukrainian market share, and then after some negotiations under German international cooperation company GIZ continued in 2021.

Results: The platform mitigated the risks associated with manual document processing and enhanced the efficiency of customs clearance. It also streamlined customs processes, particularly for low-risk goods, thus optimizing the overall cost and time involved in service, drawing inspiration from successful cases like Dubai.

TradeLens has announced the cessation of its operations in the first quarter of 2023, citing the failure to achieve full global industry collaboration as the reason. While the platform was successfully developed, it fell short of the commercial viability required to sustain independent operations. Notably, the platform faced challenges in gaining support from key players, shippers, and freight forwarders³⁴. According to Garrido, Maersk struggled to convince shippers of the platform's added value, and freight forwarders had reservations about potential disintermediation in the logistics chain. The lack of sufficiently attractive incentives for these stakeholders contributed to the platform's discontinuation. Additionally, the perceived value proposition for information providers at terminals, port community systems, or freight forwarders was deemed low, raising questions about the incentive for sharing data with TradeLens.

³³ [Митниця підключилася до міжнародної системи відстеження переміщення морських вантажів](#)

³⁴ [Tradelens Discontinues Operations. Why You Should Care](#)

Forest Stewardship Council's Supply Chain

Date live: 2019 - Present (moved to the next stage of testing)

Stakeholders: Forest Stewardship Council, State Forestry Agency

Problem: At its core, provenance is a supply chain management problem, as wood from illegal logging operations (e.g. in primeval forests or Chernobyl zone) quickly enters the legal supply chain and then becomes almost impossible to detect. Also, forest-related supply chains still rely on paper documentation, creating systems that open the potential for fraudulent claims where bad actors can tamper with or falsify documentation. As mentioned by the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC), transaction retro verification has two major downfalls: first, it only allows investigating events that occurred in the past, once the damage has already been done; second, it only allows investigating with a very narrow and fixed scope on a particular supply chain.

Another main challenge is the need to effectively share data among thousands of companies in 120 countries involved in forestry. This problem has become key to the integration of national companies into the global system. Technical obstacles, such as the lack of a single API for data exchange and the risk of information leakage, require reliable and confidential data exchange.

Solution: In 2019, as part of the "European Green Deal," the European Union approved the "New EU Forest Strategy for 2030" which champions climate and biodiversity-friendly forest management. One vital indicator of a company's commitment to sustainability is FSC certification.³⁵ In 2021, FSC developed and piloted its first cloud-based blockchain platform. The pilot involved ten participating companies and focused on two relatively simple, "short" supply chains in Ukraine and China. Specifically in Ukraine, the piloting of this project was carried out in a certain clear sequence of actions, which ultimately ensured the success of the project. Steps of piloting included:

1. initiated gathering of expert strategists to develop a win-win strategy;
2. emphasized transparency and openness by the responsible state body;
3. agreed on the scale of the pilot (initially proposed 3-4 state-owned enterprises, then expanded to involve 15 across the entire region);
4. transitioned from local implementation to broader engagement (regional administration interacted actively with private participants);
5. ensured compliance with formal procedures and interaction guidelines with authorities;
6. designated accountable management for efficient implementation;
7. provided ongoing technical support to involved entities (state-owned and private), motivating private participants with incentives like technical assistance, ready-made solutions, and training for optimal cooperation.

³⁵ The Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) is an international non-governmental organization that promotes environmentally and socially responsible forest management. By obtaining this certification, businesses affirm that their raw materials originate from FSC-certified forests with traceable supply chains. Modern technologies have significantly streamlined the process of acquiring and validating FSC certification.

This pilot concluded in early 2022, and that led to the expectation of having a working prototype of the FSC's Next Generation Blockchain by the end of 2023 and the plan to make the platform available to general users from 2024.³⁶

Results: Blockchain has helped transform compliance and traceability of FSC materials across supply chains in several ways, including moving to digital documentation, linking trading partners to all parties handling materials back to the source, and ensuring material compliance across the supply chain without the need to disclose or identify business relationships beyond an organization's existing direct connections. Blockchain also addresses IT limitations by providing a comprehensive package of immutability, information security, and consensus, even when the parties involved are not known to each other.

Based on feedback received from participants of the project, the State Forestry Agency of Ukraine is currently considering the possibility of creating an improved second-generation "EOD" system (the unified state system of electronic timber accounting), which should improve the transparency of the timber control mechanism and allow for a full transition to modern IT technologies and tools³⁷. The implementation of the new generation of EOD should use blockchain technology to track the chain of origin of wood from the moment of logging to further sales by market participants, and subsequently to the export of wood.

E-Hryvnia CBDC

Pilot Dates: 2017 – 1st, 2023 – 2nd

Stakeholders: National Bank of Ukraine, Stellar Protocol

Problem: Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDCs) are designed to address challenges related to the evolution of payment infrastructure, aligning with global trends. They aim to promote financial stability, bolster economic security, and enhance the efficacy of monetary policy.

Solution: Since 2017 the National Bank of Ukraine (NBU) stood among the pioneering central banks globally in exploring the potential of CBDCs³⁸. In 2018, it piloted a project that launched the Electronic Hryvnia (E-Hryvnia) platform, where a limited amount of e-Hryvnia (equivalent to UAH 5,443) was issued and used for payments. To create this platform, the NBU selected the private blockchain technology, in particular the private version of the Stellar protocol. Next year the NBU published a 42-page analytical note on the results of this pilot project³⁹, although there were no further large-scale national launches of the project.

³⁶ [FSC platform](#) and [Timber Chain by iov42](#)

³⁷ [Єдина державна система електронного обліку деревини](#)

³⁸ [CBDC tracker](#)

³⁹ [Analytical Report on the E-hryvnia Pilot Project](#)

In 2021, Ukraine legalized using the NBU digital currency for certain types of payments by individuals and businesses within Ukraine according to the "Law on Payment Services." The aforementioned changes to the legislation of Ukraine made it possible to launch another pilot project on a private initiative⁴⁰. The project envisaged the use of public blockchain with asset-control capabilities for issuers through the two-level system, when the central bank issues CBDCs but it delegates the functions of interaction with end users to commercial banks or other intermediaries⁴¹. According to the opinion of the Deputy Governor of the NBU, the tested model prompts exploration into the economic viability of a commercial intermediary's role in this context⁴².

October 2022 witnessed the registration of "е-гривня" and "е-hryvnia" trademarks owned by the NBU, while the next month marked the announcement of the draft concept for E-Hryvnia, outlining its potential use in retail cashless payments, virtual assets transactions, and cross-border payments⁴³.

Results: Experts and participants in the financial services market anticipated a positive impact of the e-hryvnia across the following areas: facilitating retail non-cash payments, particularly in peer-to-peer (P2P) transfers between individuals and e-commerce transactions including cross-border payments; utilization of e-hryvnia for targeted social payments (G2P) especially 'programmable' targeted funds to ensure that state payments can only be used for specific purposes or within a defined period⁴⁴. From a technological point of view, the latter is realized through conditional transfers, where smart contracts could trigger payments in the e-Hryvnia.

The pilot projects demonstrated the benefits of introducing the E-Hryvnia in line with Ukraine's broader strategy to modernize its economy, strengthen the digitalization of public services, and promote the growth of technology companies within the unique tax and legal space for IT businesses in Diia City. However, there have been no further large-scale national launches of the project. Some of the constraints are based on several challenges and obstacles that lie ahead for CBDC implementation in Ukraine, including the balance between user freedoms and security. Full E-Hryvnia implementation depends on significant modernization of Ukraine's payment infrastructure. As stated, the NBU is actively exploring diverse use cases for E-Hryvnia, which will shape its design and key features.

⁴⁰ [TASCOMBANK Hryvnia-nominated Electronic Money Pilot Report Recommends Adoption of Blockchain to Transform the Payment Landscape of Ukraine](#)

⁴¹ [Electronic hryvnia Pilot TASCOMBANK](#), p.13

⁴² [Electronic hryvnia Pilot TASCOMBANK](#), p.6

⁴³ [NBU Unveils E-hryvnia Concept to Payment Market and Virtual Asset Market Participants](#)

⁴⁴ [Опитування щодо можливості запровадження е-гривні](#)

Real Estate Rights Registration

Date live: 2023 - Present

Stakeholders: Virtual Assets of Ukraine, Parliamentary group "Blockchain4Ukraine", DFINITY, Kitsoft

Problem: The challenges of property registries are focused on maintaining the immutability of information and preventing data corruption. By eliminating the ability to make changes to records, blockchain technology aims to create a more accessible environment for both Ukrainian and foreign investors in the real estate market. The approach also seeks to improve market liquidity and streamline business registration processes, as all real estate transactions and rights should now be registered for legal validity and require notarial certification, resulting in the current paper-based, bureaucratic, slow, and expensive transaction process. This outdated system is unable to integrate smart contracts, digital tokens, and other financial technology innovations that have emerged with blockchain and web3 technologies.

Solution: In 2023 [the Public Union "Virtual Assets of Ukraine"](#) (VAU) started realizing the ambitious initiative "Blockchain4Ukraine" based on the roadmap with the Parliamentary Group "Blockchain4Ukraine" and memorandums of cooperation with the Ministry of Digital Transformation and the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine. As part of this initiative, the development of a Blockchain Estate Registry (BER) was launched, guided by the doctoral thesis of O.Konashevych⁴⁵. The project proposes creating a multi-chain system that combines reliable public networks like Ethereum and Bitcoin, known for their data immutability and operational reliability. Government functions would be encoded in 'smart laws' — smart contracts designed for regulatory purposes. The plan also includes maintaining the current registry system and offering BER as an alternative. This approach provides people with the choice between traditional and blockchain systems, allowing them to transfer their property records to the blockchain to benefit from web3 technologies.

Results: The project is in its early stages; by early 2024, the team had completed the development of an application prototype on the Internet Computer Protocol and Polygon networks to demonstrate to public officials the potential benefits and functionality of the proposed blockchain-based real estate registry⁴⁶. The technical developer of the prototype was Kitsoft, supported by a crypto-grant from the Dfinity Foundation (Switzerland)⁴⁷.

⁴⁵ [Tokenization of real estate on blockchain](#)

⁴⁶ [BLOCKCHAIN ESTATE REGISTRY IN UKRAINE](#)

⁴⁷ [В Україні розробили перший у світі прототип Блокчейн Реєстру Власності](#)

CONCLUSION

Findings

The results of our study generally support the idea that the adoption of new technologies is a complex and non-linear process that requires significant effort, thorough testing, and a systematic approach for successful large-scale implementation. This idea is consistent with another study's conclusion that surveys of blockchains for public sector governance have thus far focused on single areas of implementation, without considering the broader applications of blockchain for public sector governance⁴⁸.

Although pursuing 'sensational implementations' for early technology adoption is not necessarily problematic, an ongoing trend in this direction has resulted in numerous isolated initiatives that lack substantial impact on the quality and transparency of public services. The observation also applies to our other finding regarding the deployment of projects on a single node controlled by one party, which was common in most early pilots, such as SETAM/OpenMarket and State Land Cadastre. However, this practice usually does not utilize the primary benefits of blockchain technology.

Another critical aspect to consider is the importance of maintaining and updating relevant technological solutions. Insights from pilots such as FSC's case and TradeLens have validated blockchain's positive attributes, including interoperability and confidentiality. These projects have demonstrated extensive data exchange capabilities, fostering confidential and secure participant communication. The result is increased transparency, openness, and integrity within the system. Furthermore, FSC showcased the smooth integration of blockchain technology into the worldwide data exchange system. It also presented an extra verification alternative for online audits, which enhances its overall efficiency.

However, other problems arose from documents and interfaces written in English that were not fully understood by Ukrainian users. This language barrier created challenges in interactions between countries and systems, especially in Ukraine.

One of the keys to the success of the effort was further strengthened by effective management practices, including the introduction of key support mechanisms such as the establishment of an "IT nanny" and a help desk. These support structures played a key role in providing technical assistance to regular users of the service, including private companies and individual users, and this was particularly important in the early stages of project implementation.

Some pilot projects were characterized by ineffective management, lack of interest, loss of data, limited vision, and a focus on short-term benefits. As a result, the overall

⁴⁸ [Government by Code? Blockchain Applications to Public Sector Governance](#)

outcome was unclear, there was no obvious purpose for the initiatives, and it was difficult to identify key indicators, evaluate data, and build confidence in the project's results. The latter can be attributed to broader factors, such as a general lack of awareness and motivation about the technology and its capabilities among decision-makers at the official level. In addition, there's a lack of interested and motivated blockchain specialists and institutions.

The property registry cases showed that a limited understanding of the extent to which the system needs to change has led to hesitation, as not everyone is willing or interested in removing unnecessary intermediaries from the process. On the other hand, the indecision and apprehension of senior management and government decision-makers were attributed to potential challenges in scaling blockchain solutions. There are concerns about unknown implications that could lead to violations of human rights, international law, Sybil attacks, and other unforeseen consequences.

Recommendations

The following is a summary of issues and suggestions that decision-makers can use when implementing web3 projects in government services. These are based on the TOE framework described in the International Experience Overview.

Challenges	Recommendations
Technological: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design issues - Scalability - Process change cost - Low throughput rate - Security 	<p>Defining the specific socially useful purpose of utilizing blockchain technology.</p> <p>Developing joint standards, such as EVM, and collaborating with standardization organizations can ensure interoperability and simplicity between different blockchain solutions. It is important to make the concept of multichain integral to the project from its inception.</p> <p>Establishing partnerships and leveraging existing widely-used solutions are crucial for cost optimization.</p> <p>Providing an accessible and secure traceability environment for developers and participants.</p> <p>Providing technical assistance to ordinary users (private businesses and users) to avoid suboptimal implementations with increased security risks and operational inefficiencies; when analyzing data, ordinary employees require visualization and tips for better understanding.</p>

Organizational:

- Resistance to change
- Capacity-building
- Technical skills

Engaging participants voluntarily supports the further potential for scaling them into more advanced and developed forms, resulting in broader and more effective solutions.

Implementing customized educational programs can improve comprehension of blockchain technology and its potential application in various domains.

Removing the fear of potential punishment for all participants with explanations of purpose and control only over the goal of pilots (not people).

Environmental:

- Enabling legislative support
- Lack of awareness
- Legal issues
- Collaboration among government agencies

Starting with smaller-scale applications (with a focus on specific regions, companies, or industries) helps with speed and affordability.

Presenting web3 solutions as optional alternatives to existing public service solutions during the initial stages of implementation.

The successful implementation of a project requires careful preparation, technical expertise, and the cooperation of all parties involved. The application of blockchain technologies can increase efficiency, transparency, and reliability, contributing to resource conservation and compliance with global standards. When it comes to public services, it is important to consider that facilitating projects in areas that do not require systemic legislative changes, especially those that do not involve immediate transactions or a lot of personal data, is more straightforward for the efficiency of public governance. Using non-personalized information on a public blockchain usually does not require the creation of a specific legal basis.

However, at the national level, systemic solutions are imperative, as demonstrated by the real estate registry and the CBDC cases, and it is necessary to create a new legal framework by modifying the existing one. Therefore, it is reasonable to prioritize projects in areas that don't require such extensive changes (e.g., register of business names, other intellectual property, decentralized autonomous identity). Still, in the process of introducing blockchain technologies in government services, it is always crucial to ensure compliance with all official procedural requirements, both national and EU-related.

Consistent with previous research, current applications of blockchain technology in Ukraine are often isolated to limited-scale pilot projects, but we believe in the broad potential of web3 for government services. It is also noteworthy that previous studies have suggested the creation of indexes of public sector blockchain implementations, a

concept that has not been extensively explored⁴⁹. Equally compelling is the need for further research to delve deeper into the reasons for governments' limited adoption of blockchain technology on a larger scale.

⁴⁹ [Government by Code? Blockchain Applications to Public Sector Governance](#)

EXPERT DISCUSSION

On June 5, 2024, an online meeting was held with the participation of 50+ representatives of government agencies (Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine, National Bank of Ukraine, State Service of Special Communications and Information Protection of Ukraine, etc.), research projects (FSC, E-Hryvnia) and business (Juscutum, AMLbot, Stobox) where the following issues were discussed:

- *Challenges and opportunities of implementing web3 in the public sector*
- *Ways of such implementation and necessary support (including legal support)*
- *Relevant use cases for implementation*
- *Requests for additional information or research*

Below are the key insights gathered during the meeting.

Opportunities

Experts shared their vision regarding the potential for implementing blockchain technology in Ukraine, emphasizing opportunities for ensuring information security and decentralization. They see the potential for using blockchain to enhance data protection reliability, as well as data accessibility and integrity. Special attention was paid to the possibility of using web3 to increase trust. At the same time, it was noted that little attention is given to opportunities in cybersecurity protection.

It was noted that Ukraine has significant potential in the field of web3 technologies and is recognized as one of the leading countries even on a global scale. We have a strong business community ready to participate and often provide necessary services to the state at their own expense, which also contributes to the export opportunities of these businesses. However, the state does not always provide a clear request dictated by a long-term strategy.

Challenges

One of the main obstacles today is the lack of knowledge about the benefits and relevant cases, as well as experience working with web3 technologies in the public sector both in Ukraine and worldwide. It was noted that working on pilot projects can be valuable, even if they do not produce the most relevant cases, as this provides practical experience and a better understanding of where web3 can have a greater impact.

The full implementation of web3 would require serious reform of existing processes and structures. The ability to make these changes depends on political will, the presence of a comprehensive transition strategy, and transparent regulatory acts that

would provide civil servants with more opportunities to implement technologies. Some existing regulations, such as legislation on state registries in Ukraine or GDPR and HIPAA worldwide, impose certain restrictions on the use of fully decentralized and open systems, which also need to be considered.

Additionally, the issues of the cost of development and maintenance for the technological solutions and the lack of specialized professionals are important. At the same time, it is recognized that the impact of web3 on govtech is a global trend in which all countries will be involved in one way or another, and it is only a matter of time.

Implementation Paths

It was repeatedly emphasized that web3 technologies, although having their advantages, are not a "silver bullet" and can only provide benefits as part of comprehensive programs aimed, for example, at reducing corruption or developing the industry. Therefore, it is important to understand at what level the implementation takes place - state, sectoral, or at the level of a separate state function, and how web3 applications will be integrated with other initiatives at this level.

It is necessary to create an organization (such as a sandbox for innovative technologies) that will facilitate the safe implementation of technologies, provide the appropriate regulatory framework, and ensure trust in the results of experimentation. Also, the transition to web3 will be effective when users do not need to make significant changes to their usual ways of using services.

Application Areas

Identified areas where work is being done or interest has been shown:

- Protection, processing, and transmission of sensitive personal data, such as medical, using zero-knowledge proof (ZK-proof) technologies
- P2P trading in the energy sector
- Various state registries (court decisions, declarations, voters, excise taxes, etc.)
- Integration with the "Trembita" system and notary services
- Voting (including prioritizing recovery projects)

Requests for information

To address the issue of awareness of the use of technologies, one of the most valuable resources could be a library of international precedents for the use of web3 in the public sector, their results, and an assessment of their relevance to Ukraine's needs. It is also important to have certain guidelines and best practices for civil servants who want to pilot these technologies in their work.

Information on the existing web3 user base in Ukraine and current trends would be useful. It is also important to consider aspects of European integration, such as compatibility with EU regulations and standards, particularly with the EU digital wallet.

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